

Thyroid Profile in Menstrual Disorders

Helema Yasser Al-Massawi

Baghdad AL-Karkh Health Directorate, Baghdad, Iraq

Aminah Hilal Khallaf

Al-Rusafa Health Directorate, Baghdad, Iraq

Reem Mohammed Badea Al-Badri

Al-Rusafa Health Directorate, Baghdad, Iraq

Abstract

Background: Thyroid dysfunction is an important endocrine cause of menstrual abnormalities. Evaluation of thyroid function is recommended in women presenting with menstrual disorders in order to avoid unnecessary invasive procedures such as curettage or hysterectomy. **Aim of the Study:** To determine the prevalence of thyroid disorders and evaluate their relationship with menstrual abnormalities. **Method:** This prospective case-control study was conducted at Imamein Kadhimein Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq. A total of 100 women were included, comprising 50 women with menstrual disorders (study group) and 50 women with normal menstrual cycles (control group). Detailed history, clinical examination, and laboratory investigations were performed for all participants. Thyroid function tests including TSH, T3, and T4 were measured and compared between the two groups to determine the association between thyroid dysfunction and menstrual disorders. **Results:** Menorrhagia was the most common presentation (86%), followed by amenorrhea (10%) and dysmenorrhea (4%). The peak age of presentation was 30–40 years (48%). Infertility was found in 4% of the study group compared with 2% in the control group, and 58% of patients were multiparous. Thyroid dysfunction was detected in 32% of women with menstrual disorders, including 20% hypothyroidism and 12% hyperthyroidism, whereas all women in the control group had normal thyroid function. Significant differences were found in thyroid hormone levels between the two groups ($P < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Thyroid dysfunction appears to be an important contributing factor to menstrual disturbances, particularly among women in the late reproductive age group. Screening for thyroid abnormalities should be considered in women presenting with menstrual disorders.

Introduction

The menstrual cycle is a complex physiological process that involves coordinated interactions between the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, ovaries, and endometrium. Cyclic secretion of gonadotropins and steroid hormones produces functional and morphological changes in the ovaries, leading to follicular maturation, ovulation, and formation of the corpus luteum. Parallel hormonal changes occur in the endometrium, preparing it either for implantation of a fertilized ovum or for shedding during menstruation when pregnancy does not occur [1]. The normal menstrual cycle can be divided into two major components: the ovarian cycle and the uterine cycle [2]. The ovarian cycle consists of two phases: the

follicular phase and the luteal phase. The follicular phase involves the development and maturation of ovarian follicles under the influence of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), resulting in the selection of a dominant follicle. This phase usually lasts 10–14 days and largely determines the variability in the total length of the menstrual cycle. The luteal phase begins after ovulation and continues until the onset of menstruation, typically lasting about 14 days [2]. A normal menstrual cycle ranges from 21 to 35 days with menstrual bleeding lasting 2–6 days and an average blood loss of 20–60 mL [3,4]. The uterine cycle corresponds to the ovarian cycle and includes three phases: menstrual, proliferative, and secretory phases [2]. During the menstrual phase, which begins on the

More Information

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first day of bleeding, the functional layer of the endometrium is shed due to hormonal withdrawal [8]. In the proliferative phase, rising estrogen levels stimulate regeneration and proliferation of the endometrial lining in preparation for possible implantation [2]. Following ovulation, the secretory phase occurs under the influence of progesterone secreted by the corpus luteum. During this phase, endometrial glands secrete glycogen and other substances necessary for implantation. If fertilization does not occur, regression of the corpus luteum leads to a decline in progesterone and estrogen levels, causing endometrial ischemia and eventual menstruation [5,6]. Hormonal regulation of the menstrual cycle involves intricate feedback mechanisms between the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis. Estradiol levels rise during the follicular phase and trigger a surge of luteinizing hormone (LH), which induces ovulation approximately 24–36 hours later [2]. Progesterone levels peak during the luteal phase and decline before menstruation if pregnancy does not occur [5]. Thyroid hormones play an important role in reproductive physiology. Thyroid dysfunction is more common in women and occurs four to five times more frequently than in men [6,7]. Both hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism can disrupt the normal menstrual cycle through alterations in sex hormone metabolism, gonadotropin secretion, and ovarian function [8,9]. Hyperthyroidism is commonly associated with oligomenorrhea or amenorrhea, whereas hypothyroidism may lead to menorrhagia and frequent menstrual bleeding [7]. Thyroid dysfunction may also impair ovulation, shorten the luteal phase, and contribute to infertility or early pregnancy loss [10,11]. Menstrual disorders are common gynecological problems affecting women of reproductive age and include conditions such as amenorrhea, dysmenorrhea, and menorrhagia [12]. Amenorrhea refers to the absence of menstruation and may be primary or secondary depending on the onset of menstrual failure [2]. Dysmenorrhea is characterized by painful menstruation and may be primary, occurring without pelvic pathology, or secondary, resulting from underlying pelvic disease such as endometriosis or adenomyosis [13,14]. Menorrhagia, defined as excessive menstrual bleeding exceeding 80 mL per cycle or lasting more than seven days, affects approximately 10–30% of reproductive-aged women and up to 50% of perimenopausal women [6,15].

Aim of the Study: to determine the prevalence of thyroid disorders and assess their correlation with menstrual disorders

Method

This prospective case–control study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Imamein Kadhimain Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq, over a

period of twelve months from June 1, 2014 to May 31, 2015. The aim of the study was to evaluate the association between thyroid function and menstrual disorders. A total of 100 women were included in the study and divided into two groups. The control group consisted of 50 women with normal menstrual cycles, while the study group included 50 women presenting with menstrual disorders but without any pathological lesions of the genital tract. All participants provided verbal consent before enrollment in the study. Participants were recruited from the outpatient gynecology clinic. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that included demographic and clinical variables such as age, parity, age at menarche, menstrual cycle characteristics, presenting complaints, and thyroid status.

Inclusion Criteria

Women were eligible for participation if they met the following criteria:

1. Age between 18 and 43 years.
2. All parity groups were included.
3. Participants were apparently euthyroid clinically.

Exclusion Criteria

Women were excluded if they had:

1. Organic lesions of the genital tract such as uterine fibroids.
2. Use of hormonal medications, including oral contraceptive pills.
3. Bleeding disorders.
4. Use of an intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD).
5. Pregnancy.

All participants underwent detailed history taking, including present illness and past or family history of thyroid disease. A general physical examination was also performed, assessing body build, body weight, thyroid enlargement, tachycardia, and tremors. Blood samples were collected from all participants for measurement of serum triiodothyronine (TT3), thyroxine (TT4), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels. Blood samples were collected in plain tubes, and serum was separated and stored at low temperature until analysis. Hormonal assays were performed using a Minividas analyzer. The reference ranges used were TT3: 0.95–2.5 nmol/L, TT4: 60–120 nmol/L, and TSH: 0.25–5 mIU/mL.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 22 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). Results were presented as frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations, and ranges. The Chi-square test was used to assess associations between qualitative variables. Differences between means were evaluated using the Student's t-test, while ANOVA was used for

comparisons involving more than two groups. A P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included 50 women with menstrual disorders (study group) and 50 women with normal menstrual cycles (control group). The mean age was 32.46 ± 6.85 years in the study group and 30.34 ± 5.95 years in the control group, with no significant difference ($P = 0.28$).

Most participants were fertile, accounting for 94% in the study group and 88% in the control group, while infertility was reported in 4% and 2%, respectively ($P = 0.21$). The mean parity was 2.8 ± 1.8 in the study group and 2.1 ± 1.4 in the control group. Overall, no statistically significant differences were found between the two groups regarding age, fertility, or parity ($P > 0.05$), as in table 1.

Table 1: Age, Fertility and Parity Distribution in Study and Control Group

		Study group		Control group		P value
		No	%	No	%	
Age (years)	<25	7	14.0	9	18.0	0.285
	25---29	10	20.0	9	18.0	
	30---34	12	24.0	20	40.0	
	35---39	12	24.0	8	16.0	
	=>40	9	18.0	4	8.0	
	Mean±SD (Range)	32.46±6.84 (18-43)		30.34±5.95 (18-43)		
Fertility	Fertile	47	94.0	44	88.0	0.212
	Infertile	2	4.0	1	2.0	
	Not married	1	2.0	5	10.0	
Parity	Para0	6	12.8	8	18.2	0.098
	Para1	7	14.9	4	9.1	
	Para2	7	14.9	15	34.1	
	Para3	12	25.5	11	25.0	
	Para4 & more	15	31.9	6	13.6	
	Mean±SD(Range)	2.8±1.8 (0-7)		2.1±1.4 (0-6)		

*Significant using Pearson Chi-square test at 0.05 level

Table 2 shows the clinical presentation, thyroid status, and family history in both groups. In the study group, menorrhagia was the most common presentation (86%), followed by amenorrhea (10%) and dysmenorrhea (4%), while all controls had normal cycles. Regarding thyroid status, 68% had normal thyroid function, 12% had hyperthyroidism, and 20%

had hypothyroidism, whereas all controls were euthyroid, showing a significant difference ($P = 0.0001$). A positive family history was reported in 2% for hyperthyroidism, 8% for hypothyroidism, and 8% for menorrhagia, while 82% had no family history. The difference in family history between groups was not statistically significant ($P = 0.180$).

Table 2: Presentation, Thyroid Status and Family History of Study and Control Group

		Study group		Control group		P value
		No	%	No	%	
Presentation	Menorrhagea	43	86.0	-	-	-
	Amenorrhea	5	10.0	-	-	-
	Dysmenorrhea	2	4.0	-	-	-
Thyroid status	Hyper	6	12.0	-	-	-
	Normal/Euothyroid	34	68.0	50	100.0	-
	Hypo	10	20.0	-	-	-
Family history	Hyperthyroid	1	2.0	-	-	-
	Hypothyroid	4	8.0	-	-	-
	Menorrhagea	4	8.0	-	-	-
	No	41	82.0	50	100.0	-

*Significant using Pearson Chi-square test at 0.05 level

Table 3 presents the age at menarche, thyroid surgical history, menstrual cycle characteristics, and thyroid

medication use in both groups. The mean age at menarche was 12.4 ± 1.3 years in the study group and

12.4 ± 1.0 years in the control group, showing no significant difference (P = 0.552). A history of thyroidectomy was reported in 8% of the study group, while none in the control group (P = 0.448). Most patients in the study group had irregular cycles (82%),

while all controls had normal cycles (P = 0.458). Additionally, 12% of the study group were taking thyroid medications, whereas none in the control group used such medications (P = 0.906), indicating no statistically significant differences.

Table 3: Menarche Age, Surgical and Medical History of Thyroid Disease, and Cycle Details in Study and Control Group

		Study group		Control group		P value
		No	%	No	%	
Age at menarche (years)	11	15	30.0	10	20.0	0.552
	12	15	30.0	18	36.0	
	13	11	22.0	15	30.0	
	14	5	10.0	6	12.0	
	15	3	6.0	1	2.0	
	16	1	2.0	-	-	
	Mean±SD(Range)	12.4±1.3 (11-16)		12.4±1.0 (11-15)		
Surgical history of thyroid	Thyroidectomy	4	8.0	-	-	-
	Partial thyroidectomy	-	-	-	-	
	No	46	92.0	50	100.0	
Cycle details	Heavy irregular	2	4.0	-	-	-
	Oligo irregular	-	-	-	-	
	Irregular	41	82.0	-	-	
	No cycle	2	4.0	-	-	
	Normal	5	10.0	50	100.0	
Drug history for thyroid	Yes	6	12.0	-	-	-
	No	44	88.0	50	100.0	

*Significant using Pearson Chi-square test at 0.05 level

The mean level of TSH in study group was 2.90±1.99 and range (0.10-7.00) MIU/L while in control group the mean was 3.39±2.00 and range (0.30-11.50) MIU/L. So 4 patients had low TSH level in study group and 10

patients (20%) had high TSH level while only 2 patients in control group had high TSH level. The P value was 0.004 which is statistically significant. As shown in table 4.

Table 4: TSH Level in Study and Control Group

		Study group		Control group		P value
		No	%	No	%	
TSH (MIU/L)	Low	4	8.0	-	-	0.004*
	Normal (0.25--5)	36	72.0	48	96.0	
	High	10	20.0	2	4.0	
TSH (MIU/L)	<0.5	7	14.0	6	12.0	0.006*
	0.5---	5	10.0	-	-	
	1.0---	4	8.0	-	-	
	1.5---	1	2.0	-	-	
	2.0---	2	4.0	4	8.0	
	2.5---	2	4.0	1	2.0	
	3.0---	11	22.0	16	32.0	
	3.5---	3	6.0	11	22.0	
	4.0---	4	8.0	7	14.0	
	4.5---	-	-	3	6.0	
	5.0---	5	10.0	-	-	
	5.5---	1	2.0	-	-	
	=>6.0	5	10.0	2	4.0	

*Significance of difference using Students-t-test for two independent means at 0.05 level

The mean T4 level in study group was 87.28±30.19 and range (25-150) nmol/L, while the mean was 92.06±13.37 and range (65-120) nmol/L. so 8 patients (16%) had low T4 level and 5 patients (10%) had high T4

level in study group. While all control group had normal T4 level. The P value was 0.005 which is statistically significant as shown in table 5.

Table 5: T4 Level in Study and Control Group

		Study group		Control group		P value
		No	%	No	%	
T4 (nmol/L)	Low	8	16.0	-	-	-
	Normal (60-120)	37	74.0	50	100.0	
	High	5	10.0	-	-	
T4 (nmol/L)	<50	5	10.0	-	-	0.005*
	50---	3	6.0	-	-	
	60---	5	10.0	1	2.0	
	70---	4	8.0	6	12.0	
	80---	10	20.0	18	36.0	
	90---	4	8.0	8	16.0	
	100---	7	14.0	9	18.0	
	110---	1	2.0	5	10.0	
	120---	6	12.0	3	6.0	
	130---	-	-	-	-	
	=>140	5	10.0	-	-	

*Significance of difference using Students-t-test for two independent means at 0.05 level

The mean level was 1.27±1.14 and range was (0.10-5.60) nmol/L in study group while the mean was 1.12±0.95 and range (0.10-2.50) nmol/L in control

group. The P value was 0.0001 which is statistically significant as shown in table 6.

Table 6: T3 Level in Study and Control Group

		Study group		Control group		P value
		No	%	No	%	
T3 (nmol/L)	Low	24	48.0	23	46.0	0.056
	Normal (0.95-2.5)	21	42.0	27	54.0	
	High	5	10.0	-	-	
T3 (nmol/L)	<0.5	11	22.0	22	44.0	0.0001*
	0.5---	14	28.0	2	4.0	
	1.0---	10	20.0	7	14.0	
	1.5---	5	10.0	-	-	
	2.0---	5	10.0	17	34.0	
	2.5---	-	-	2	4.0	
	3.0---	2	4.0	-	-	
	3.5---	1	2.0	-	-	
	=>4.0	2	4.0	-	-	

*Significance of difference using Students-t-test for two independent means at 0.05 level

Discussion

Thyroid dysfunction is recognized as an important endocrine cause of menstrual abnormalities, and evaluation of thyroid function is recommended in women presenting with menstrual disorders to avoid unnecessary invasive procedures such as curettage or hysterectomy [16]. Thyroid hormones influence reproductive physiology through their effects on ovarian function, sex hormone metabolism, and the

hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis. Hypothyroidism, in particular, has been associated with a wide spectrum of reproductive disturbances ranging from abnormal sexual development to menstrual irregularities and infertility [17,18]. In the present study, the peak age of menstrual disorders was observed between 30–40 years, accounting for 48% of cases. This finding is consistent with previous studies conducted by Neelu Sharma and Anita Sharma [19], as well as Pilli et al. [20],

who reported that the majority of dysfunctional uterine bleeding (DUB) cases occurred between 21–40 years of age. Similarly, Doifode and Fernandes [21] observed that 48.33% of hypothyroid patients with DUB were between 31–40 years, which further supports the findings of the present study. Regarding fertility, 4% of women in the study group were infertile compared with 2% in the control group, though the difference was not statistically significant. Similar observations were reported by Joshi et al., who found infertility in 6% of hypothyroid women, compared with 5% in euthyroid women with goiter and 2.4% in healthy controls [22]. In addition, Lincoln et al. found that 2.3% of infertile women had elevated serum TSH levels, suggesting the presence of overt or subclinical hypothyroidism [23]. Another study by Arojoki et al. reported elevated TSH levels in 4% of infertile women and overt hypothyroidism in 3.3% [24]. These findings suggest that thyroid dysfunction may contribute to infertility in a subset of women. Parity distribution in the current study showed that 58% of patients had parity of three or more, suggesting that menstrual disorders may be more common among multiparous women. Similar results were reported by Mehrotra et al., who observed 46% multiparous and 34% grand multiparous women among patients with menstrual disorders [25]. Pilli et al. also reported a high proportion (87%) of multiparous women with dysfunctional uterine bleeding [20], supporting the findings of the present study. Menorrhagia was the most common presenting complaint, observed in 86% of cases. This finding is consistent with earlier reports indicating that heavy menstrual bleeding is one of the most frequent gynecological complaints in clinical practice [15]. Pilli et al. reported menorrhagia in 34% of cases, while Mehrotra et al. found an incidence of 54.2%, both supporting the predominance of menorrhagia among menstrual disorders [20,26]. More than 30% of women with menstrual disorders in the present study had thyroid dysfunction, which is consistent with studies by Neha Sharma and others demonstrating a strong association between thyroid abnormalities and menstrual disturbances [16,27]. In contrast, all participants in the control group had normal thyroid function, and the difference between the two groups was highly statistically significant ($P = 0.0001$). These findings emphasize the important role of thyroid dysfunction in the etiology of menstrual abnormalities. Among patients with thyroid dysfunction, hypothyroidism (20%) was more common than hyperthyroidism (12%). Similar findings were reported by Mukherjee and Ghosh, who observed 44% hypothyroidism among women with menstrual disorders [28], and Doifode and Fernandes, who reported 28.17% hypothyroidism in patients with DUB [21]. Wilansky and Greisman also reported a

prevalence of 22.38% early hypothyroidism among clinically euthyroid women with menorrhagia [29]. Serum TSH remains the most sensitive indicator of thyroid function, reflecting thyroid hormone activity in peripheral tissues [30]. In the present study, there was a significant difference in TSH levels between the study and control groups ($P = 0.004$), indicating a strong association between thyroid dysfunction and menstrual disorders. Additionally, significant differences were observed in T3 and T4 levels, with P values of 0.0001 and 0.005 respectively, further supporting the role of thyroid abnormalities in the development of menstrual disturbances. These findings are consistent with the observations reported by Neelu Sharma, who also demonstrated a significant association between thyroid hormone abnormalities and menstrual irregularities [19].

Conclusion

Thyroid dysfunction can be a potential factor for menstrual disturbances especially in women in their late reproductive age groups with high parity.

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